

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

PROTECTION OF THE NEUTRAL WIRE FROM ITS BREAKAGE, FROM OVERLOAD CURRENTS AND SHORT-CIRCUIT CURRENTS IN NETWORKS WITH NONLINEAR LOADS

Aleksandr Kobozev

Ph.D.

Abstract

With the appearance of nonlinear loads in networks, problems have arisen with the reliability of neutral wire protections. The 3rd harmonic currents, which are arithmetically added up in the neutral wire, increase its load, so the protection of the neutral wire from overload currents becomes relevant. When constructing such protection, it is necessary to take into account the current of the 3rd harmonic. An increase in the current in the neutral wire leads to the fact that the current in the neutral wire becomes commensurate with the current of a single-phase short circuit. Therefore, the reliability of protection against single-phase short circuits decreases if the undesirable influence of the 3rd harmonic currents is not eliminated. The construction of protection against the break of the neutral conductor and the resulting overvoltages is based on the analysis of the nature of the force function, i.e., the dependence of the change in the sum of the squares of the phase currents over time. The 3rd harmonic currents for this analysis of the force function are an undesirable interference. Thus, when constructing different protections, the values of the effective current values must be measured both taking into account the currents of the 3rd harmonic and without taking them into account. Therefore, an appropriate method has been developed, while it does not use the mathematical apparatus of the discrete Fourier transform, as redundant for switch trippers. This is consistent with the purpose of creating such methods and algorithm for constructing protections that are based on the analysis of current values measured by the methods adopted in the construction of current protections. This allows the algorithm for the construction of such protections, together with the maximum current protections, to be implemented in the circuit breaker trips. In this case, the infrastructure of protection of electric networks is significantly reduced.

Keywords: Neutral wire protection, force function, current harmonics.

1. Introduction.

As a result of the appearance of non-linear loads (computer, etc.) in three-phase networks, additional problems may arise with the protection of the neutral wire (N -wires). Before considering these problems and the proposed ways to solve them, we will briefly point out the existing problems with protection - N -wires at linear loads.

There are various ways to protect against N -wire breakage and the resulting overvoltages. To build a protection against the break of the neutral wire, the analysis of the value of the reverse sequence current has recently been used. Measuring transducers are used to determine the current value. They contain differentiating induction measuring current transducers, as well as a reverse sequence voltage filter. Therefore, it is very difficult to implement such protection in a microprocessor-based circuit breaker trip. Therefore, protection against the break of the N -wire based on the analysis of the reverse sequence current is implemented in special devices. According to [1], the analysis of the reverse sequence current is implemented, for example, in the BMRZ-102 units (R&D Center "Mechatronics") and the MiCOM P126 relay (Schneider Electric). When using the above and other similar devices, the circuit breaker trip is used only as an actuator element for disconnecting the network when a control signal arrives at it. The above method of protection against breakage N wires and overvoltages - provides for a significant increase in the infrastructure of the network protection system. At the same time, the circuit breakers in this system, in addition to current protection, perform only

the function of an actuator. In order for the circuit breakers to also perform the functions of protection against N -wire breakage and the resulting overvoltages, it is necessary that the algorithm of such protections can be implemented in the microprocessor unit of the circuit breaker trip. To do this, it is necessary that only information from current sensors included in the circuit breakers is sufficient to construct these protections.

The paper presents [2] method for constructing protections against N -wire breakage and the resulting overvoltages based on the analysis of the force function of the electric network. This function $F_s(t)$ is the dependence of the change in time of the sum of squares of phase currents. This means that for the construction of N - wire protections, information only from current sensors is sufficient, and therefore the algorithm for constructing such protections can be implemented in a trip unit switch.

The construction of the protection against the breakage N of the wire is based on the analysis of the nature of the force function in $F_s(t)$ the steady state. The analytic expression of a function $F_s(t)$ is defined by the following expression:

$$F_s(t) = [i_a(t)]^2 + [i_b(t)]^2 + [i_c(t)]^2 \quad (1)$$

where $i_a(t)$, $i_b(t)$ and $i_c(t)$ - are the dependencies of the change in time of phase currents.

If the moduli of the phase currents are the same and equal to the phase value I_f ($I_a = I_b = I_c = I_f$), then the expression of the force function of the network without nonlinear loads $F_s(t)$ will be as follows:

$$F_s(t) = 3I_f^2 + [I_f^2 \cos 2\omega t + I_f^2 \cos 2(\omega t - 2\pi/3) + I_f^2 \cos 2(\omega t + 2\pi/3)] = F_{sd}(t) + F_{sa}(t) \quad (2),$$

where $F_{sd}(t)$ is the constant of the component, and the $F_{sa}(t)$ variable of the component.

As follows from expression (2), if in addition to the equality of the modules of phase currents, the equality of angles between the vectors of phase currents is also preserved, then the variable component $F_{sa}(t)$ will be equal to zero. This property of the force function makes it possible to use its analysis to determine the absence or presence of a break N in the wire. For example, if in the current system of a real network the modules of phase currents are made equal in value - with the help of equalization coefficients ($I'_a = I'_b = I'_c$), then in the absence of an open N wire, the variable component of the force function of such a transformed network $F'_{sa}(t)$ will be equal to zero. And in case of a break in the N - wire, when the angles between the vectors of the phase currents are no longer the same and equal to $2\pi/3$, a variable component will appear $F'_{sa}(t)$ and its value will characterize the value of the overvoltage. The considered in [2] method of constructing protection against open N -wires refers to the case of the absence of higher current harmonics in the network. In the presence of higher current harmonics, in particular, currents of the 3rd harmonic, it is necessary to take into account their influence on the reliability of protection. This requires an appropriate method of analyzing the force function.

3rd harmonic currents also affect the reliability of protection against single-phase short-circuit currents and overload currents. After all, the summation of the 3rd harmonic currents of all phases in the wire leads to a situation in which the value of the current in the N - wire becomes commensurate with the possible values of single-phase short-circuit currents. But when constructing a N -wire protection against overload currents, 3-harmonic currents must be taken into account. Thus, there is a problem of developing a method for selectively determining the effective current values - in some cases it is necessary not to take into account 3-harmonic currents, and in others to take into account. Taking into account the above, the main goal of this work was to create N -wire protections in networks with nonlinear loads based on the analysis of only information from the circuit breaker current sensors. This makes it possible to implement protection algorithms in microprocessor-based circuit breaker trips. To achieve this goal, the task was set to develop a method for determining the values of the 1st and 3rd harmonic currents without using the well-known discrete Fourier transform apparatus, as it is excessive for circuit breaker releases.

It was also necessary to develop methods for constructing reliable protection against currents of single-phase short-circuits by eliminating undesirable interference from 3rd harmonic currents based on the analysis of the force function, in which the influence of 3rd harmonic currents on the reliability of protection should be excluded.

2. Main results

2.1 Method for determining the values of the effective values of the currents of the 1st and 3rd harmonics

One of the possible methods that make it possible to determine the effective values of the effective values of the currents of higher harmonics is the mathematical apparatus of Fourier decomposition. This method makes it possible to determine the values of currents of different harmonics, in particular, currents of the 1st and 3rd harmonics. However, in the current protections that are used in the circuit breaker trips, this mathematical apparatus is not used. Therefore, a method for determining the values of the effective values of the currents of the 1st and 3rd harmonics was developed, which uses the methods for determining the effective current values accepted for current protection.

The method for determining the effective value of the currents of the 1st and 3rd harmonics is based on the consequence of failure to meet the requirements of the Nyquist-Shannon-Kotelnikov theorem [3] and [4]. According to the specified requirements of the theorem, the sampling rate of the analog signal should be at least 2 times higher than the frequency f_3 of the 3rd harmonic. If the time range of sampling is limited to a single period of current variation, then the sampling rate should be used at 3 times the frequency f_3 of the 3rd harmonic current. If the requirement of this theorem on the sampling rate is not met, the f_d consequence will be an inevitable distortion of the value of the third-harmonic current in the total phase current. Therefore, it seems productive to deliberately choose such a sampling rate at which the **distortion** of the value of the third harmonic current, in the direction of its decrease, will be the maximum possible, namely, equal to zero. Such a sampling rate, as will be shown below, is the frequency of the current of the 3rd harmonic, the value of which is equal to $f_3=150$ Hz.

Let us consider the case when, with continuous monitoring of the effective current value, the beginning of the discrete current values i_j occurs at the moment when the 3rd harmonic current passes through the zero value. At a sampling rate equal to the 3rd harmonic current frequency ($f_d=f_3=150$ Hz) all discrete current values i_j will not contain the 3rd harmonic current. This means that the measured value of the effective current will be minimal I_{min} and equal to the current of the first harmonic:

$$I_{min} = I_1 \quad (3)$$

Now let's consider a case in which the discrete values of the dependence $i(t)$ will start at the time of the passage of the 3rd harmonic current through its maximum value $\sqrt{2}I_3$. In this case, all discrete values of the 3rd harmonic current i_j will be the same and equal $\sqrt{2}I_3$. Therefore, in this case, the measured value of the effective current value will be the maximum I_{max} and is determined by the expression:

$$I_{max} = \sqrt{I_1^2 + 2I_3^2} \quad (4)$$

Thus, with continuous monitoring of the value of the effective value of the current, we obtain the dependence $I = f(t)$, in which the value of the current changes from its minimum value I_{min} to the maximum I_{max} . From the result of monitoring the values of the effective value of the current, we can determine the value of the current of the 1st harmonic by expression (3). It should

be noted that in order to ensure sufficient accuracy in determining the extreme values of the effective current values I_{min} and I_{max} , the time interval between the next readings of discrete current values should be sufficiently small. The value of the specified time interval should correspond to the slip frequency f_s , which significantly exceeds the frequency of the current of the 3rd harmonic, for example, $f_s=1500$ Hz.

Now let's consider how the results of monitoring the values of the effective current value can be used to determine the value of the 3rd harmonic current.

The maximum effective value of the current I_{max} , as shown earlier, is determined by the expression (4). Given that $I_{min} = I_1$, consider the sum of the squares I_{max}^2 and I_{min}^2 :

$$I_{max}^2 + I_{min}^2 = 2I_1^2 + 2I_3^2 \quad (5)$$

It follows from equation (4) that the effective value of the current taking into account the currents of the 1st and 3rd harmonics $I_{(1+3)}$ will be determined by the following expression:

$$I_{(1+3)} = \sqrt{0,5(I_{max}^2 + I_{min}^2)} \quad (6)$$

Thus, the value at the root of half of the sum of the squares of the extreme values of the effective current value is indeed the value of the current taking into account the currents of the 1st and 3rd harmonics.

If the value of the 1st harmonic current I_1 is known as $I_1 = I_{min}$, then from equation (4) we obtain that the value of the 3rd harmonic current I_3 will be determined by the following expression:

$$I_3 = \sqrt{I_{(1+3)}^2 - I_{min}^2} = \sqrt{0,5(I_{max}^2 - I_{min}^2)} \quad (7)$$

The obtained expressions (2), (6) and (7) to determine the effective values of currents in the 1st and 3rd harmonics, as well as their sums, can be used in the construction of different types of protection N -wires.

It should be noted that in the considered method for determining the values of the 1st and 3rd harmonic currents, methods for determining the effective current values used in the construction of current protections are used. Therefore, the considered technique can be implemented in the circuit breaker trip.

2.2. Methods for constructing various types of protection – wires N

2.2.1. Construction of protection against wire breakage N and emerging overvoltages

When constructing a protection against N -wire breakage in a network without nonlinear loads [2] a real system of phase currents is converted into a system with identical modules of phase current vectors. Since in networks with nonlinear loads, 3rd harmonic currents do not affect overvoltages when the N -wire is broken, it is sufficient to equalize only the values of the effective values of the 1st harmonic currents. For this purpose, the expression (3) is used to find the value of the effective value of the 1st harmonic current. After the values of the 1st harmonic currents in the phases are determined, the equalization coefficients are determined K_{1a} , K_{1b} and K_{1c} .

Then, with the help of equalization coefficients, a transformed current system is formed, in which the values of the phase currents of the 1st harmonic are the same.

In such a converted current system, if there is no break in the N -wire, the variable component $F'_{sa}(t)$, will be present as part of the force function $F'_s(t)$, due to 3rd harmonic currents. There fore, in order to construct the protection of the N -wire in the absence of its breakage, it is necessary to analyze not the nature of the entire force function, but only the envelope line of the minimum values of the force function. This envelope line does not contain the values of the 3rd harmonic current. And since the values of the effective values of the 1st harmonic currents are the same ($I'_{1a} = I'_{1b} = I'_{1c}$), the envelope curve of the minimum values of the force function F'_{min} is the dependence of $F'_{min} = f(t)$ is essentially a constant component of the force function for the 1st harmonic currents $F_{sd}(t) = 3I_1^2$. Thus, the criterion for the absence of an N - wire break is the constancy in the value of the dependence $F'_{min} = f(t)$.

Fig.1 Nature of the force function of the reduced current system before and after N-wire break

Fig.1a shows the nature of the force function and its component for the case when the value of the 3rd harmonic current is 43% of the value of the 1st harmonic current. As can be seen from Fig. 1 $aF_s(t) F_{sd}(t)F_{sa}(t)$, the minimum value of the force function F'_{smin} does not take into account the currents of the 3rd harmonic. Therefore, the value F'_{smin} in the absence of an N-wire break turns out to be equal to the value of the constant component of the force function F'_{sd} .

in the case when two power feeders of apartment buildings are connected to the line, and the break in the N-wire occurred at the entrance of the main panel of one of the houses. In this case, the force function of the converted current system $F'_s(t)$ will contain the variable component $F'_{sa}(t)$. This component is due to both the 3rd harmonic currents of the undamaged part of the network, and the non-symmetry of the 1st harmonic currents of the damaged part of the network.

Now let's consider what nature the force function will have in the event of an N-wire break. For example,

Fig.2 Dependence of the value of overvoltage ΔU_f on the value of the variable component of the force function F_{sa}

Fig.1b shows a graph of the force function for the case of a partial break the N-wire. As can be seen from the graph, in addition to the constant component F'_{sd} , the force function includes the variable component caused by the currents of the 1st and 3rd harmonics. The variable components of the force function, which

change with the frequencies of the currents of the 1st and 3rd harmonics, change over time from their minimum values to the maximum. At the same time, in the envelope line of the minimum values of the force function $F'_{min} = f(t)$, depending on the values of the 3rd

harmonic currents $F'_{s1}(t)$, will not be taken into account. Therefore, the results of the dependency analysis $F'_{min} = f(t)$ for networks with nonlinear loads are identical to the analysis of the force function for networks without nonlinear loads. Fig.2 shows the dependence obtained from the results of a machine experiment $\Delta U_f = f(F_{sa})$ for networks without higher harmonics. The value of the variable component F_{sa} is presented in relative units to the value of the constant component $F_{sd} = 3I_f^2$. The experiments were carried out for the most dangerous combination of phase loads $Z_a > (Z_b = Z_c)$ from the point of view of the value of overvoltage. As the calculations showed, if $F_{sa} \geq 0.32$, then the overvoltage value $F_{sd} \Delta U_f$ will be more than $0.2 \cdot U_f$ so the network should be disconnected in 15 seconds.

Thus, the criterion for the occurrence of an N -wire break is the change over time in the dependence of the minimum value of the force function $F'_{min} = f(t)$, which is the force function of the 1st harmonic currents. At the same time, the value of the effective value of the time component of the specified force function characterizes the overvoltages in the phases when the N -wire is broken $F'_1 = f(t)$. At the same time, the value of the effective value of F'_{sa} the time component of the specified force function characterizes the overvoltages in the phases when the N -wire is broken, which can be determined from the dependence $\Delta U_f = f(F_{sa})$.

Summing up, let's formulate the essence of the algorithm for implementing protection against N -wire breakage. First, the values of the 1st harmonic currents in the phases are determined using the method for determining the values of the 1st and 3rd harmonic currents. After that, the equalization coefficients for the 1st harmonic currents are determined, and with their help the values of the effective values of the currents of all three phases of the converted network are determined. determine the dependencies of the change in time of currents in each of the phases of the transformed current system - $i'_a(t)$, $i'_b(t)$ and $i'_c(t)$. After that, the force function of the converted current system $F'_s(t)$ and its components - $F'_{sd}(t)$ and $F'_{sa}(t)$. After that, the nature of the envelope curve of the minimum values of the force function - F'_{min} dependence $F'_{min} = f(t)$ is analyzed. If the instantaneous values F'_{min} do not change with time, then it is concluded that there is no break in the N -wire. If the values F'_{min} of the change over time, then it is concluded that there is break a the N -wire. Since the dependence $F'_{min} = f(t)$ is a variable component of the force function of the currents of the 1st harmonic $F'_1 = f(t)$, then the value of the effective value of the variable component of this function $F'_{sa} = F'_1$, determines the value of the expected overvoltage ΔU .

2.2.2. Construction of protection N -wires against overload currents.

First, based on the instantaneous values of currents i_j in phases a, b, and c, the dependence of the current in the N -wire on time is determined - the dependence $i_N = f(t)$. Then, from the analysis of the dependence $i_N = f(t)$, in accordance with the method for determining the values of the 1st and 3rd harmonic currents, the dependence of the change over time of the effective value of the current in the N -wire is determined - the dependence $I_N = f(t)$.

From the dependence $I_N = f(t)$, the extreme values of the current are determined - the values I_{Nmin} and I_{Nmax} and the effective current value in the N -wire, taking into account the 1st and 3rd harmonic currents, using the expression $I_{N(1+3)} = \sqrt{0,5(I_{Nmax}^2 + I_{Nmin}^2)}$. After that, the current value $I_{N(1+3)}$ is compared with the overload current setting value I_{sd} , and if $I_{N(1+3)} \geq I_{sd}$, a control signal is generated.

2.2.3. Construction of protection for N -wires of single-phase short circuits

Based on the sum of instantaneous current values i_j in phases a, b, and c, the dependence of the current value in the N -wire on time is determined - the dependence $i_N = f(t)$. Then, from the analysis of the dependence $i_N = f(t)$, the dependence of the change in the effective current value in the N -wire over time is determined - the dependence $I_N = f(t)$. After that, the minimum current value I_{Nmin} is determined. Then, the 1st harmonic current value is determined as $I_{N1} = I_{Nmin}$ and compared with the short-circuit current setting value I_{kz} . If $I_{N1} \geq I_{kz}$, a control signal is generated by the control element IE to activate the protection.

Algorithm of the microprocessor release operation when constructing N -wire protection

The algorithm of the microprocessor release operation for implementing N -wire protection against breakage, short-circuit currents, and breakage is shown in Fig. 3. The mathematical operations of the algorithm are presented in the form of modules, but they do not physically exist.

N -wire protection channel against breakage and resulting overvoltages

The basis of the N -wire break protection algorithm is the analysis of the force function. Such an analysis can be performed by continuously monitoring the current during the time interval Δt between readings of discrete current values. In this case, the microprocessor's performance must be sufficiently high.

Force analysis is possible in a repetitive short-term mode of operation, in which, in the first time interval ($\Delta t = 20 \text{ ms}$), measurements are made and current values are stored in memory during the first period, and in the second time interval, the force function is analyzed.

Fig.3 Algorithm for constructing protections against N-wire breakage, overload currents and single-phase short-circuit

In module 1, from analog signals from current sensors with a sampling frequency significantly higher than the frequency of the third harmonic current (for example, $f_s = 1500 \text{ Hz}$), the dependencies of the instantaneous values of phase currents on time are determined. The obtained dependencies $i_a = f(t)$, $i_b = f(t)$ и $i_c = f(t)$ are stored in the microprocessor memory.

In module 2, from the dependencies $i_a = f(t)$, $i_b = f(t)$ и $i_c = f(t)$, the effective values of the phase currents are determined at each slip step Δt_s , corresponding to the slip frequency $f_s = 1500 \text{ Hz}$. The discrete current values are determined with a sampling frequency of $f_d = 150 \text{ Hz}$. In the same module, the dependence of the change in the effective values of the phase currents is determined—the dependencies $I_a = f(t)$, $I_b = f(t)$ and $I_c = f(t)$. From these dependencies, the extreme values of currents in each of their

phases are determined - the values I_{min} and I_{max} . In the same module, from the found values I_{min} and I_{max} , the effective values of the 1st harmonic currents are determined from the expression $I_1 = I_{min}$. In the same module, based on the found values of the 1st harmonic currents in each phase—the values I_{1a} and I_{3a} , I_{1b} and I_{3b} , I_{1c} and I_{3c} , the equalization coefficients for the 1st harmonic phase currents are determined K_{1a} , K_{1b} and K_{1c} .

In Module 3, the initial dependencies of the phase currents $i_a(t)$, $i_b(t)$ and $i_c(t)$ on time are multiplied by the equalization coefficients K_{1a} , K_{1b} and K_{1c} . This determines the converted dependencies of the phase currents of the reduced current system over time – dependencies - $i'_a(t)$, $i'_b(t)$ and $i'_c(t)$.

In module 4, the force function $F'_s(t)$ is determined for the converted current system - $i'_a(t)$, $i'_b(t)$ and $i'_c(t)$. In the same module, the dependencies of the

constant component of the force function $F'_{sd}(t)$ and the variable component $F'_{sa}(t)$ on time are determined.

In module 5, the value F'_{sa} is compared with the permissible value, and if $F'_{sa} \geq 0,32F'_{sd}$, a "Yes" signal is generated and sent to module 6 (the executive element).

N-wire overload current protection channel.

In module 7, the dependencies $i_a = f(t)$, $i_b = f(t)$ and $i_c = f(t)$ obtained in module 1 are used to determine the dependence of the current in the *N*-wire $i_N = f(t)$ on time. From the dependence $i_N = f(t)$, the dependence $I_N = f(t)$ and the extreme values of the effective current – the values I_{Nmin} and I_{Nmax} – are determined.

In module 8, from the found values I_{Nmin} and I_{Nmax} , the effective value of the current in the *N*-wire is determined, taking into account the 1st and 3rd harmonic currents, using the expression $I_{N(1+3)} = \sqrt{0,5(I_{Nmax}^2 + I_{Nmin}^2)}$

In module 9, the current value $I_{N(1+3)}$ is compared with the overload current setting value I_{sd} . If $I_{N(1+3)} \geq I_{sd}$, a control signal is generated by the actuator IE of module 6 to activate the protection.

Single-phase short-circuit current protection channel

In module 10, the effective values of the 1st harmonic currents are determined from the expression $I_{N1} = I_{Nmin}$

In module 11, the current value I_{N1} is compared with the short-circuit current setting value I_{kz} . If $I_{N1} \geq I_{kz}$, a control signal is generated by the actuator IE of module 6 to activate the protection

3. Summary

The task of creating N-wire protections in networks with nonlinear loads based solely on the analysis of information from current sensors has been solved. The peculiarities of the flow of 3rd harmonic currents in networks with nonlinear loads make it necessary, when constructing various protections for N-wires, to take into account 3rd harmonic currents in some cases and not to take them into account in others. To this end, a method has been developed for determining the magnitude of 1st and 3rd harmonic currents without using the well-known discrete Fourier transform, which is excessive for circuit breaker releases. This method forms the basis for the construction of N-wire protection.

Thus, when designing protection against overload currents, the current value is analyzed taking into account the 1st and 3rd harmonic currents, and when designing protection against single-phase short circuits, the current value is analyzed without taking into account the 3rd harmonic current.

The basis for constructing protection against N-wire breakage and resulting overvoltages is an analysis of the force function of the transformed current system, in which the effective values of the 1st harmonic currents of all phases are made equal by means of equalization coefficients. The force function of such a current system generally contains a constant and a variable component. An important factor in the design of N-wire protection is that the composition of the force function depends on the state of the wire. If there is no N-wire break, then only a constant component exists in the composition of the force function. When the N-wire breaks, an alternating component also arises, the magnitude of which determines the magnitude of the overvoltage.

All of the N-wire protections considered are based on the analysis of data from current sensors only, and the same methods used in the construction of current protections are used to measure current values. This allows, as stated in the objectives of the work, the algorithm for constructing neutral wire protections to be implemented, together with maximum current protections, in circuit breaker releases. In this case, the infrastructure of electrical network protections is significantly reduced.

References

1. A. M. Ershov, A. V. Khlopova, A. I. Sidorov . «Neutral Wire Break Monitoring Device in 0.38 kV Networks», Power Tehnology and Engineering, 05 September 2020, pages 434-437
2. A. Kobozev, «Neutral wire break protection and redundancy failures by force function analysis», Journal of science, Lion, № 68/2025, pages 19-23
3. N. Korystova "Kotelnikov-Shannon theorem", Internet resource "Graphics & media lab", www.graphicon.ru/oldgr/courses/cg_el00/kotelnikov.pdf
4. Mironova, "The Use of the Kotelnikov-Shannon Theorem in Time Series Interpolation", Proceedings of the IONA-2001 Conference, pages 1-41